

42 **Abstract**

43 Although current antiretroviral therapy (ART) has increased life expectancy, a cure for
44 human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) remains elusive due to the persistence of the virus in
45 tissue reservoirs. In the present study, we sought to elucidate the relationship between
46 antiretrovirals (ARVs) and viral expression in the spleen. We performed mass spectrometry
47 imaging (MSI) of 6 different ARVs, RNAscope *in situ* hybridization for viral RNA and
48 immunohistochemistry of three different fibrosis markers in the spleens of 8 uninfected and 10
49 reverse transcriptase simian-human immunodeficiency virus (RT-SHIV)-infected rhesus
50 macaques (infected for 6 weeks) that had been dosed for 10 days with combination ART. Using
51 MATLAB, computational quantitative imaging analysis was performed to evaluate the spatial
52 and pharmacological relationships between the 6 ARVs, viral RNA and fibrotic deposition. In
53 these spleens, >50% of the spleen tissue area was not covered by any detectable ARV
54 response (any concentration above the limits of detection for individual ARVs). The median
55 spatial ARV coverage across all tissues was driven by maraviroc followed by efavirenz. Yet,
56 >50% of RNA-positive cells were not exposed to any detectable ARV. Quantifiable maraviroc
57 and efavirenz colocalization with RNA-positive cells was usually greater than the *in vitro* IC₅₀.
58 Fibrosis markers covered more than 50% of the spleen tissue area and had negative
59 relationships with the cumulative ARV coverages. Our findings suggest that heterogeneous
60 ARV spatial distribution must be considered when evaluating viral persistence in lymphoid
61 tissue reservoirs.

62

63 **Introduction**

64 For over three decades, the mainstay for the treatment of human immunodeficiency
65 virus (HIV) is antiretroviral therapy (ART).(1) Although combination ART has resulted in
66 undetectable plasma viral load (pVL) and an increased life expectancy comparable to those
67 living without HIV, there is not yet a cure.(2) Moreover, lifelong adherence to daily ART is
68 required, as plasma viral rebound occurs after treatment disruption.

69 The major barrier to a cure for HIV is the persistence of HIV reservoirs in the body's
70 tissues.(3–5) The primary tissues in which reservoirs reside are secondary lymphoid tissues,
71 including the gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT), lymph nodes (LNs), and the spleen.(5, 6)
72 Even though the spleen is an important secondary lymphoid tissue in the immune system, it
73 also plays an important role in the circulatory system.(7) Because of the spleen's unique dual
74 primary functions, the biology of HIV reservoir persistence and composition may be unique
75 within the spleen compared to other secondary lymphoid tissues.

76 While the hypothesis of ongoing viral replication within lymphoid tissues was put forth,
77 this being the cause of reservoir maintenance remains controversial.(8) Nolan et al noted that
78 the spleens from 5 participants virally suppressed on ART at the time of death contained
79 clonally expanding cells with identical proviral genomes, highlighting the importance of the
80 spleen tissue.(9) And recently, Bozzi et al did not detect evidence of genetic changes in HIV
81 sequences – either in blood or tissues – in patients after years of ART, indicating the growing
82 evidence towards clonal expansion as the primary driver of reservoir maintenance.(10) In light
83 of this controversy, it has been previously suggested that the persistence of long-lived infected
84 cells may be related to the limited exposure of ARVs.(8, 11) This is imperative as experimental
85 cure strategies, such as “Kick-and-Kill”, will require adequate ART concentrations within deep
86 tissue reservoirs to prevent viral persistence.(12)

87 Historically, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) has been
88 the gold standard for quantifying ARV concentrations in biological matrices. Our group has

89 previously reported ARV concentrations of homogenized spleens from nonhuman primates
90 (NHPs) and humans, and noted large variation of splenic concentrations compared to those in
91 plasma (7.5-fold lower to 9.5-fold higher, depending on the drug).(13) But sample preparation –
92 specifically whole-tissue homogenization – results in the loss of important spatial information.
93 Elucidating the geographical distribution of ARVs within tissues is an important next step to
94 study pharmacological efficacy of drugs.(6) Indeed, novel mass spectrometry imaging (MSI)
95 methods in the gut, brain, and LNs have illuminated heterogeneous ARV distribution within
96 those tissue reservoirs.(14–16)

97 Analyses of splenic inflammation and fibrosis in those living with HIV are limited.
98 Histological findings within postmortem spleens of virally suppressed HIV+ patients include
99 inflammation and lymphoid hyperplasia.(17) Given that the spleen is a fibrous organ(18),
100 additional fibrosis may provide a barrier to drug diffusion and distribution. However, the
101 influence of fibrosis on splenic drug distribution is unknown.

102 Herein, we utilize a novel MSI method known as infrared matrix-assisted laser
103 desorption electrospray ionization (IR-MALDESI) to image 6 ARVs, RNAscope ISH to image
104 viral RNA, and immunohistochemistry (IHC) for fibrosis markers in the spleens of uninfected
105 NHPs and NHPs infected with reverse transcriptase simian-human immunodeficiency virus (RT-
106 SHIV). Quantitative, computational imaging analysis methods were employed to understand the
107 spatial relationships between these important drug treatment factors.

108

109 **Methods**

110 *NHP study and tissue collection*

111 The NHP study and tissue collection has been described previously.(13) Briefly, 18
112 rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*) were used in this study. Eight NHPs (6 males, 2 females)
113 were left uninfected and 10 NHPs (6 males, 4 females) were infected for 6 weeks with RT-SHIV.
114 pVL was monitored during infection period. After 6 weeks, all animals were dosed to steady-

115 state (10 days) with ARV doses based on previously reported effective treatment regimens in
116 this model. All NHPs received daily subcutaneous doses of 30 mg/kg of body weight of
117 emtricitabine (FTC) and 16 mg/kg of body weight of tenofovir (TFV) plus one of the following
118 oral combinations: 200 mg of efavirenz (EFV) daily plus 100 mg of raltegravir (RAL) twice daily
119 (FTER regimen; n =9) or 150 mg/kg of maraviroc (MVC) twice daily plus 270 mg/kg of
120 atazanavir (ATV) twice daily (FTMA regimen; n = 9). One day after the final dose, NHPs were
121 euthanized using phenobarbital and necropsy was performed. At necropsy, spleens were
122 collected from each NHP and snap frozen with liquid nitrogen. Plasma and spleen tissue viral
123 loads were measured using previously published methods.(19, 20) All relevant viral load
124 measures are reported in **Table S1** in the Supplemental Material, page 2. Spleen tissue was
125 stored at -80°C until analysis. NHP 40422, on the FTC, TFV, EFV and RAL regimen, developed
126 liver failure; this NHP was excluded from further analysis.

127

128 *Tissue sectioning*

129 The spleens from each NHP (n=18) were mounted on a specimen disc using O.C.T.
130 (Tissue-Tek; Sakura Finetek, Inc., Torrance, CA) and cryosectioned at -16°C using a Leica
131 CM1950 cryomicrotome (Leica Biosystems, Buffalo Grove, IL) at a thickness of 10 microns.
132 Sections were thaw-mounted onto positively charged glass slides (IHC and ISH) or plain glass
133 slides (IR-MALDESI). Serial sections were collected from each spleen in the following order and
134 quantity for each imaging method: IHC, 3 sections; IR-MALDESI and LC-MS/MS, 6 sections
135 (alternating); and ISH, 2 sections.

136

137 *LC-MS/MS and IR-MALDESI MSI analyses*

138 LC-MS/MS methods for spleen tissue homogenate samples have been detailed
139 previously.(13) The workflow for IR-MALDESI MSI analyses has been described in greater
140 detail by our group,(16) but is also placed within the Supplemental Material, page 3. Using

141 MATLAB, per-volumetric pixel (voxel) drug response was quantified based on calibration on
142 matched blank spleen tissue.(21) Utilizing a volumetric pixel area of 0.1 mm², section thickness
143 of 0.01 mm and a tissue density of 0.00106 g/mm³, concentrations were converted to units of
144 ng/g tissue. MSI measures both drug and endogenous information simultaneously, including a
145 marker for blood (heme). Individual and cumulative (i.e. total ARV responses from all 4 drugs)
146 ARV maps are generated. Tissue-specific ARV concentrations can be evaluated by correcting
147 for heme. The lower limits of quantification for LC-MS/MS (in ng per gram of tissue [ng/g]) were
148 0.002 for FTC and MVC, 0.005 for EFV, RAL, and ATV, and 0.02 for TFV. The limits of
149 detection for the MSI approach (in ng/g) were 110 for MVC, 130 for ATV, 170 for EFV, 1160 for
150 TFV, 1600 for FTC, and 3040 for RAL. It is important to note that these limits of detection relate
151 to the signal abundance of individual pixels in the image. Because the response to drug is not
152 uniform across the tissue, the average tissue concentration may be less than the limit of
153 detection.(22) Heterogeneity of ARV response has been evaluated by two approaches: 1) the
154 proportion of total tissue area with detectable drug; and, 2) the dynamic range (DR) of drug
155 response where detectable.

156 The IC₅₀ values used in these analyses (in ng/g) were 2.2 for MVC (23), 2.9 for RAL
157 (24), 11.9 for EFV (25), 16.6 for ATV (26), 149 for FTC (27), and 2303 for TFV.(27) To quantify
158 intra-tissue ARV heterogeneity, the unit-less DRs were calculated as follows: 10 x
159 log₁₀(maximum/minimum intensities).(28) This information is recapitulated in **Table S2** in the
160 Supplemental Material, page 4.

161

162 *RNAscope ISH analysis and IHC multiplex*

163 ISH analysis of viral RNA was performed on splenic sections using a modification of the
164 previously published RNAscope protocol.(16, 29) Specifically, frozen tissue sections on slides
165 were brought to room temperature and dried for 15 minutes, then incubated for 2 hours in 4%
166 paraformaldehyde (PFA; Electron Microscopy Sciences; Cat. No. 15714-S) fixative in PBS at

167 room temperature and then incubated in 100% ethanol for 5 min x2, then rinsed once in double-
168 distilled water (ddH₂O). Heat-induced epitope retrieval was performed by boiling slides in 1x
169 DAKO target retrieval solution pH9 (Agilent S236784-2) for 5 min, immediately transferred to PBS,
170 incubated in peroxidase blocking solution (3% H₂O₂ diluted in 1x PBS) for 10 min at room
171 temperature, followed by a rinse in double distilled water (ddH₂O).

172 Slides were incubated with the target probe SIV_{mac239} antisense (ACD; Cat. No. 314071)
173 for 2 h at 40°C, and amplification was performed using the RNAscope 2.5 HD Brown detection kit
174 (ACD; Cat. No. 322310) using 0.5x wash buffer (ACD; Cat. No. 310091) in all washing steps.
175 Slides were developed with Alexa Fluor 647-conjugated tyramide (Invitrogen; Cat. No. B40958)
176 at a 1:500 dilution for 2 minutes.

177 Slides were then stained using rabbit anti-CD4 (Abcam; Cat. No. ab133616, 0143mg/mL)
178 at 1:200 and goat anti-CD20 (Invitrogen; Cat. No. PA1-9024, 0.5 mg/mL) at 1:200 overnight. The
179 slides were then incubated with secondary donkey anti-goat-AF488 (Invitrogen; Cat. No. A11055,
180 2mg/mL) at 1:200 for one hour and donkey anti-rabbit-AF755 (Invitrogen; Cat. No. SA5-10043,
181 0.5mg/mL) at 1:200 for one hour. All staining was performed at room temperature, and slides
182 were counterstained with 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI; Invitrogen; Cat. No. D1306) at a
183 dilution of 0.5 µg/ml in ddH₂O for 10 min, cover slipped using Prolong Gold antifade mounting
184 medium, and whole tissues scanned on an AxioScan.Z1 (Zeiss) using a Plan Apochromat 20x
185 objective (Zeiss; NA = 0.8, FWD = 0.55 mm).

186 The relative amount of SIV RNA trapped within the FDC network or within infected cells
187 was estimated by quantifying the total SIV RNA signal intensity using the ISH module FISH v1.1
188 within HALO software (v3.2.1851.393, Indica Labs). We measured the signal intensity (minimum,
189 mean, and maximum) of more than 100 identifiable individual virions within B cell follicles, which
190 corresponds to 2 copies of SIV RNA, then divided by 2 to approximate the signal intensity of a
191 single copy of vRNA. Next, annotation layers were placed around putative SIV infected cells
192 based upon anatomical localization, cell morphology, and CD4 positivity; analysis of relative

193 quantity of SIV vRNA (>4 copies) confirmed designation as an SIV infected cell. Concomitantly,
194 SIV vRNA present with CD20+ BCF germinal centers were annotated as FDC-bound virions
195 based on classical morphology. Lastly, relative SIV RNA copy number within SIV RNA+ cells or
196 within the FDC-bound network was calculated as (signal intensity within SIV RNA+ cells
197 [μm^2])/(0.5 \times mean signal size for a virion).

198

199 *IHC analysis for fibrosis markers*

200 To detect collagen type 3, chromogenic immunohistochemistry (IHC) was performed on
201 frozen tissues sectioned at 10 microns. This IHC was carried out using the Leica Bond III
202 Autostainer system. Subjacent slides were dewaxed in Bond Dewax solution (AR9222) and
203 hydrated in Bond Wash solution (AR9590). Heat induced antigen retrieval for Collagen III was
204 performed for 20 min at 100°C in Bond-Epitope Retrieval solution 2 pH-9.0 (AR9640). The
205 antigen retrieval was followed with a 5 min Bond peroxide blocking step (DS9800). After
206 pretreatment, slides were incubated for 1h with Collagen III (1:25) for 30 min. Antibody detection
207 with 3,3'-diaminobenzidine (DAB) was accomplished using the Bond Intense R detection system
208 (DS9263) supplemented with the Novolink Post Primary and Novolink Polymer (Leica,
209 #RE7260-K) secondaries or with the ImmPRESS HRP Anti-Rat IgG (#MP-7444-15, Vector
210 Labs). Stained slides were dehydrated and coverslipped with Cytoseal 60 (8310-4, Thermo
211 Fisher Scientific). Positive and negative controls (no primary antibody) are included for each
212 assay. IHC stained slides were digitally imaged in the Aperio ScanScope XT (Leica) using 20x
213 objective.

214 For collagen type 1 and fibrinogen, sequential dual immunofluorescence (IF) was carried
215 out on the Bond fully-automated slide staining system (Leica Microsystems Inc., Norwell, MA)
216 using the Bond Research Detection System kit (Leica, DS9455). Slides were deparaffinized in
217 Leica Bond Dewax solution (AR9222), hydrated in Bond Wash solution (AR9590) and
218 sequentially stained for Collagen I and then Fibrinogen. Specifically, antigen retrieval for

219 Collagen I was performed for 20 min at 100°C in Bond-epitope retrieval solution 2 pH 9.0
220 (AR9640). After pretreatment, slides were incubated for 2 hours with Collagen I antibody
221 (1:100) followed with Novocastra Post Primary and Novolink Polymer (RE7159 and RE7161,
222 Leica) then TSA Cy5 (FP1117, Akoya Biosciences, Menlo Park, CA). After completion of
223 Collagen I staining, a second round of antigen retrieval was performed for 20 min at 100°C in
224 Bond-epitope retrieval solution 1 pH 6.0 (AR9961). Slides were then incubated with the
225 Fibrinogen antibody (1:1500, 2 hours) then the Novolink Polymer (RE7161, Leica) and detected
226 with TSA Cy3 (FP1046, Akoya Biosciences). Nuclei were stained with Hoechst 33258
227 (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). The stained slides were mounted with ProLong Gold antifade
228 reagent (Life Technologies, P36930). The antibodies of interest are listed in **Table S3** in the
229 Supplemental material, page 5.

230

231 *Quantitative image analysis and colocalization*

232 The workflow for quantitative imaging analysis of ARVs, fibrosis and viral RNA, has been
233 described previously(16), and is placed in detail in the Supplemental Material, page 6. Briefly,
234 image analysis and colocalization was performed using MATLAB R2020a (Mathworks, Natick,
235 MA). Final tissue-specific ARV maps generated by IR-MALDESI analyses were co-registered
236 with viral RNA binary images that preserve the areas of the viral RNA by separating the regions
237 from the background (resulting images known as “masks”) to evaluate colocalization, including
238 IC₅₀-thresholded ARV maps to assess virus colocalization with inhibitory drug concentrations.
239 This process was then repeated between fibrosis markers and ARVs. Due to the differences in
240 resolution between IHC/ISH (~0.5 µm/pixel) and IR-MALDESI (100 µm/pixel), virion, cell-
241 associated RNA (caRNA), and fibrosis markers masks were downsampled to match the resolution
242 and dimensions of the MSI data.

243

244 *Statistical analysis*

245 Data are presented as median (range). For these nonparametric data the Mann Whitney
246 *U* test was used for a) differences in total and tissue-specific individual and cumulative ARV
247 responses and; b) variance in the extent of collagen 1, collagen 3, and fibrinogen coverages
248 between uninfected and RT-SHIV⁺ spleens. Correlations were assessed via the Spearman rank
249 correlation test for relationships between a) LC-MS/MS and MSI drug concentrations; b) fibrosis
250 and ARV coverages and; c) measures of viral load. All statistical tests were performed using R
251 version 4.0.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). A p-value of <0.05 was
252 considered statistically significant. Initial MSI data processing was performed using the free,
253 open-source MSiReader software (<https://www.msireader.wordpress.ncsu.edu/>) (30), and
254 quantitative imaging analyses were performed using MATLAB software accessed through a
255 university license (<https://www.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>).

256

257 **Results**

258 *MSI analysis of ARVs in spleens*

259 As described in the Methods section, a total number of 17 NHPs were included for
260 analysis for this study. There had been no (0%) LC-MS/MS concentrations below the limit of
261 quantification (BLQ). As **Table 1** indicates, spleen ARV concentrations, as determined by
262 quantitative MSI, were modestly correlated with LC-MS/MS ARV concentrations, and only
263 reached statistical significance for EFV ($p=0.03$). Correlation plots for the individual ARVs are
264 displayed in **Figure S1** of the Supplemental Material, page 7. Compared to LC-MS/MS, MSI
265 ARV concentrations were approximately 40% lower. Given the large numbers of BLQ values by
266 MSI quantification, subsequent quantitative MSI analyses for FTC and RAL were not performed.
267 **Figure 1** displays representative images of the intensity-scaled and tissue-specific MSI images
268 of the distribution of NHP 42707, an RT-SHIV⁺ NHP treated with the FTC, TFV, EFV and RAL
269 regimen. Heme was measured on 37% of this tissue, similar to its presence on 40% (range, 17-
270 67%) for all tissues. All analyses focused on tissue-specific ARV concentrations to ascertain

271 ARV concentrations in tissue versus the vascular space. To visualize the tissue-specific
272 response, **Table 2** reports the percentage of the spleen area that registered drug response,
273 both total and tissue-specific. The tissue-specific cumulative (whole-regimen) drug response
274 was a median 42% (range, 2-80%) of the spleen tissue area. When focusing on the tissue-
275 specific response, drug concentrations were reduced by approximately 20%, although this was
276 not statistically significant. Of all ARVs, MVC had the highest coverage across spleen tissue
277 (median 71%), with most concentrations exceeding the *in vitro* IC₅₀ value. ARV distribution
278 patterns were heterogeneous as indicated by dynamic ranges summarized in **Table S4** in the
279 Supplemental Material, page 8.

280 Examining the coverage of ARVs in spleen tissue slices, in all 17 NHPs, a median of
281 97% of voxels with detectable drug was due to only one ARV (**Figure 2**). Across all NHPs,
282 these ARVs were EFV or MVC, dependent on regimen. There was a sharp decline in the
283 number of voxels that had more than one drug. Sixteen spleens had 2 ARVs colocalized, but
284 this accounted for less than 5% of the tissue area. Twelve NHPs had 3 ARVs colocalized,
285 accounting for only 0.3% of tissue area; and 4 NHPs had all 4 ARVs colocalized in a very small
286 percentage of tissue area, ranging from 0.3-3.6%. Overall, across the NHPs, EFV or MVC
287 contributed approximately 99% of the detectable total, cumulative coverage.

288

289 *Cell-associated RNA and colocalization with ARVs*

290 Representative images of caRNA and detectable drug concentrations are seen in **Figure**
291 **3**. The cell-associated RNA viral load (copies per square millimeter of tissue) was 7.1 (range,
292 1.6-28.6 copies/mm²; **Table S5** in the Supplemental Material, page 9), which amounted to
293 0.002% (range, 0.002-0.004%) of the tissue area. ARVs were only found to co-localize with
294 caRNA cells in 5 of 9 NHPs, driven by EFV (46%) and MVC (14%), as seen in **Table 3**. RAL
295 and ATV were not measured colocally with any vRNA⁺ infected cells. Of note, the FDC-trapped

296 virions were predominantly located in the B cell follicles, as seen in **Figure S2** of the
297 Supplemental Material, page 10.

298

299 *Quantitative imaging analysis of fibrosis markers with ARVs*

300 Fibrosis markers covered 62% (range, 49-76%) of the downsampled tissue area.

301 Between the uninfected and RT-SHIV⁺ NHPs, there was no significant difference in percent
302 coverages of any marker. Correlations between fibrosis marker coverage and individual ARVs
303 were not statistically significant, but there was a negative relationship between total tissue area
304 covered by ARVs and total tissue area covered by fibrosis markers, (**Figure S3**, Supplemental
305 Material, page 11). Only collagen type 3 had a significant negative relationship with total ARV
306 distribution ($\rho = -0.5$; $p = 0.03$).

307

308 **Discussion**

309 This study explored the spatial relationship of ARVs, RT-SHIV RNA, and fibrosis
310 markers in the spleens of NHPs using multiple quantitative imaging modalities. The ability to
311 detect FTC and RAL proved to be particularly challenging by MSI in spleen tissue, where limits
312 of detection were $>10\times$ their respective IC_{50} values. Therefore, those were excluded from
313 calculations related to the percent area above inhibitory concentrations in Table 1. We noted
314 that for spleen tissue, approximately 20% of the drug response measured was associated with
315 heme, and was likely associated with blood. After isolating ARV distribution within tissue, drug
316 distribution was still noted to be diffused throughout the tissue, and the extent of diffusion was
317 drug dependent. Approximately 50% of drug concentrations were above the IC_{50} estimates for
318 TFV, and nearly 100% across all ARVs. When evaluating TFV, EFV, and MVC, drug detection
319 colocalized with $<50\%$ of caRNA. However, when detected, these concentrations were above
320 the IC_{50} values. Finally, while we found a relationship between higher fibrosis marker

321 concentrations and lower drug concentrations for EFV, fibrosis markers may not independently
322 explain low ARV coverage overall at least at these early time points post infection.

323 Previous LC-MS/MS spleen tissue analyses in these NHPs had shown that the three
324 highest ARV concentrations came from MVC, EFV, and TFV.(13) This aligns well with our
325 rankings of the percent of the spleen tissue area occupied by these ARVs using IR-MALDESI as
326 well as data observed from the mesenteric LNs from these same NHPs.(16) The imaging
327 analyses also demonstrated that these ARV distributions were spread diffusely throughout the
328 spleen and were not necessarily localized to one morphological region. The degree of heme
329 association observed in this study is not surprising given the spleen's role in
330 erythrophagocytosis and iron metabolism.(7)

331 The RNAscope analyses permitted us to identify where FDC-trapped virions and caRNA
332 are located within the spleen tissue. As expected, virions were predominantly located within the
333 B cell follicles, where they would be trapped. (29, 31, 32) Compared to the LNs from these
334 same NHPs, the caRNA viral load was approximately 10-fold lower in the spleen.(16) This
335 difference had been observed in a previous 26-week longitudinal study of SIV-infected NHPs,
336 where the spleen's contribution to the total viral burden was <1% before and after chronic
337 ART.(33) Given that the primary site of infection is within the secondary lymphoid tissue portion
338 of the spleen (e.g. the white pulp), it is conceivable that after normalizing to the white pulp tissue
339 only, more similarities to the LNs could be seen. We did note the significant relationship
340 between the size of the FDC reservoir and the caRNA viral load ($\rho=0.8$, $p=0.01$). This is
341 aligned with previous findings that demonstrated the correlation of the size of the FDC reservoir
342 and the number of productively infected cells within lymphoid tissues.(31)

343 The finding of incomplete coverage of ARVs with caRNA is similar to our findings with
344 the GI tract tissue (both ileum and rectum), and mesenteric LNs from these same NHPs(14, 16)
345 and add to the growing evidence that heterogeneous ARV distribution contributes to viral
346 persistence and expression in reservoir tissues. However, in all of these other tissues, nearly

347 80% of the caRNA was colocalized with at least one ARV, at concentrations exceeding IC_{50}
348 values.(14) Furthermore, large differences in caRNA viral loads seen in the present study in the
349 spleen compared to other known tissue reservoirs were demonstrated previously.(12, 16, 33–
350 36)

351 Previous studies hypothesized the role of fibrosis to potentially limit drug disposition in
352 lymphoid tissues, especially in LNs.(37, 38) Through IHC imaging and quantitative analysis,
353 over 50% of NHP spleen tissue was occupied by one of three fibrosis markers studied. Contrary
354 to previous data in mesenteric LNs from these same NHPs (15), no statistical differences in
355 fibrosis marker concentrations were noted between the spleens of uninfected and RT-SHIV⁺
356 NHPs. However, given that the spleen is a highly fibrous organ at baseline due to the extensive
357 and fibrillar white pulp region, detectable increases in fibrosis may be minimal over this short
358 period of time of infection (7 weeks) in this study.(7) Since the viral burden was also lower than
359 other tissues, there would reasonably be less immune activation and lower increases in the
360 transforming growth factor $\beta 1$ (TGF- $\beta 1$) signaling, which has been previously shown to
361 correspond to the collagen deposition.(38–40) Nonetheless, we observed a negative
362 relationship amount of collagen 3 and total ARV tissue distribution from the MSI approach ($\rho =$
363 -0.5 , $p = 0.03$), lending credence to the hypothesis that for some drugs, fibrosis may limit drug
364 distribution.

365 The spleen may not be as large of a viral reservoir as GALT or LNs, and this might be
366 due to the cellular protective role of the intracellular metabolites of FTC and TFV. Both parent
367 compounds are biotransformed into their active metabolites (FTC triphosphate [FTCtp] and TFV
368 diphosphate [TFVdp] via intracellular phosphorylation. Devanathan et al previously showed that
369 the splenic molar percentages of FTCtp and TFVdp in these spleens, as measured by LC-
370 MS/MS, were 22.3% and 80.3%, respectively.(13) In the LNs and ileal and rectal tissues, these
371 percentages are approximately 5%.(41, 42) In the present study, MSI FTC and TFV
372 concentrations were low, and coverage across the tissue, minimal. Therefore, because the

373 active metabolites may be more pharmacologically prevalent, those higher intracellular
374 concentrations could have provided a greater magnitude of cellular protection against viral
375 infection within the spleen. As the sensitivity of the MSI technology precluded the examination of
376 the distribution of the phosphorylated metabolites, this warrants future investigation.

377 Recently, within the context of HIV cure research, non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase
378 inhibitors (NNRTIs) have demonstrated pyroptotic activity by increasing the intracellular
379 processing of Gag and Gag-Pol within MT4, a transformed T cell line, in a concentration-
380 dependent manner; 50% cytotoxicity occurred at EFV concentrations approximately 1.71 μ M
381 (~540 ng/mL).(43) This was further demonstrated in resting and activated primary CD4 T cells,
382 with 50% cell death observed at concentrations ~500 ng/mL.(44) In the 4 infected NHPs herein,
383 median EFV concentrations via MSI and LC-MS/MS were 66 and 183 ng/g, respectively.
384 Interestingly, in our tissues, the number of infected cells detected displayed a negative
385 relationship with percent EFV coverage across the spleen tissue ($\rho = -0.8$, $p = 0.2$; data not
386 shown). Further exploration of this finding with tissue-resident cells (e.g. CD4 T cells within the
387 spleen) is warranted.

388 There are limitations to this study. First, these analyses represent a single point in time
389 (10 days following ART); therefore, it is difficult to extrapolate tissue ARV distribution across a
390 dosing interval, specifically at the times of maximum concentrations, to elucidate dynamic
391 diffusion processes. However, longitudinal sampling across a dosing interval would require a
392 large number of animals which would be technically challenging to implement. Second, a tissue
393 slice, while 10 microns thick, represents only one two-dimensional examination of a three-
394 dimensional organ. It is conceivable that different sections may have different viral RNA
395 responses and extents of fibrosis. To mitigate this, our measures utilized sections in the middle
396 of the spleens of NHPs to account for potential heterogeneity in responses.

397 Third, we found lower IR-MALDESI sensitivity to ARVs in spleen tissue compared to
398 other tissues from these same animals. Tissue matrix effects were particularly challenging due

399 to either analytical interference from high blood plasma content of these tissues or a higher
400 endogenous response in the spleen tissue compared to other tissues. Therefore, limits of
401 detection for FTC and RAL, in particular, tended to be higher than their respective IC_{50} values,
402 and precluded quantitative analyses. Fourth, the resolution of MSI images ($100 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) is
403 lower than IHC/ISH images ($0.5 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$).^(45, 46) To overlay and coregister MSI and IHC/ISH
404 images, it was necessary to match all images to the resolution of the MSI data. While this likely
405 overestimates the degree of colocalization, this represents the “best case” scenario and any
406 lower colocalization would further confirm the hypothesis of heterogeneous distribution and viral
407 persistence. Nevertheless, the process of downsampling provides novel visualizations of ARVs
408 alongside ISH and IHC images. Further optimization of the IR-MALDESI sensitivity and
409 resolution is ongoing.

410 Due to sample limitations, we had not performed optimization and staining for
411 macrophages within the spleen tissues. However, there is growing evidence that has highlighted
412 the importance of latently infected macrophages that contribute to the HIV reservoir.^(47–49) The
413 spleen – alongside the blood and lungs – contain the majority of latently infected
414 macrophages.⁽⁴⁹⁾ Further studies that quantify ARV concentrations within blood and tissue
415 macrophages would elucidate the potential for differential and/or inadequate penetration into
416 these important cell types. Finally, cells within tissues are not static, but in a constant state of
417 migratory flux; thus, cells likely enter and exit locations with variable ARV levels, but
418 cumulatively may encounter sufficient levels to be highly effective *in vivo*.

419 In conclusion, we demonstrated the utility of combinatorial imaging modalities to
420 evaluate ARV, viral RNA, and fibrosis distribution in the spleens of NHPs to test the hypothesis
421 that heterogeneous ARV distribution permits the persistence of virus. We showed that ARV
422 distribution is heterogeneous in the spleen tissue, although not necessarily caused by fibrosis
423 this early in infection. Yet certain drugs and tissues may be more sensitive to the effects of
424 fibrosis than others. Interestingly, less than 50% of RT-SHIV virions and infected cells were

425 exposed to any detectable ARV, suggesting that there may be a pharmacologic rationale for
426 viral persistence in the spleen. These data not only have implications for drug therapy, but also
427 have implications for the development of “kick-and-kill” cure strategies, which rely on the
428 premise of protective ARV coverage of uninfected cells during latency reversal in lymphoid
429 tissue reservoirs such as the spleen.

430
431

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- 627

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Representative intensity-scaled MSI images of the distribution of cholesterol (A), heme (B), FTC (C), TFV (D), efavirenz (E), and raltegravir (F) in an RT-SHIV⁺ NHP 42707. Percentages in the top-right corner indicate the MSI area covered by each target. Brighter colors (white and yellow) represent higher MSI signal intensities whereas darker colors (black and red) represent the converse, as indicated by the color bar on the left. Abbreviations: FTC, emtricitabine; TFV, tenofovir; EFV, efavirenz; RAL, raltegravir; MSI, mass spectrometry imaging; RT-SHIV, reverse transcriptase simian-human immunodeficiency virus; NHP, nonhuman primate.

Figure 2. Fraction of spleen area covered by one to four of the ARVs administered in the 4-drug regimen. Data above the boxplots are median (range) percentage of coverage. Sample sizes underneath percentages refer to NHPs containing the specific number of ARVs per voxel. Boxplots represent the median and 25th and 75th percentiles. Abbreviations: ARV, antiretroviral; NHP, nonhuman primate.

Figure 3. Representative images of the colocalization between cell-associated RNA (magenta) in the RT-SHIV⁺ NHP 42707: caRNA and CD20 (in green; panel A), caRNA and cumulative FTER (B), and caRNA and individual ARVs (C-F). Percentages in the top-right corner represent the degree of co-localization between ARVs and caRNA. Yellow arrows indicate locations of overlap between ARV and caRNA. Abbreviations: ARV, antiretroviral; FTC, emtricitabine; TFV, tenofovir; EFV, efavirenz; RAL, raltegravir; caRNA, cell-associated RNA; RT-SHIV, reverse transcriptase simian-human immunodeficiency virus; NHP, nonhuman primate.

Table 1. Spleen drug concentrations quantified by LC-MS/MS and MSI

ARV	N of NHPs (N BLQ for MSI)	LC-MS/MS concentration (ng/g of tissue)	MSI concentration (ng/g of tissue)	Rho	P
FTC	17 (14)	27.9 (6.5-45.2)	31.3 (1.5-60.2)	-0.5	1
TFV	17 (3)	261 (62-632)	137 (1.5-1650)	0.3	0.2
EFV	8 (1)	505 (3.8-1320)	433 (20.8-2509)	0.8	0.03
RAL	8 (5)	33.9 (4.9-71.3)	15.4 (12.7-30.6)	-1	0.3
MVC	9 (1)	281 (3.7-429)	64.7 (0.6-350)	0.7	0.1
ATV	9 (3)	17.9 (7.0-27.2)	18.2 (7.0-605)	-0.7	0.2

Data are median (range). MSI concentrations that were below the limit of quantification (BLQ) were excluded from this analysis. Correlations (rho) and associated p-values calculated by the nonparametric Spearman's rank correlation, excluding BLQ. Abbreviations: ARV, antiretroviral; FTC, emtricitabine; TFV, tenofovir; EFV, efavirenz; RAL, raltegravir; MVC, maraviroc; ATV, atazanavir; BLQ, below the limit of quantification; MSI, mass spectrometry imaging.

Table 2. Spleen area covered by total and tissue-specific drug response and the tissue-specific response greater than the respective IC₅₀

ARV	N	Total	Tissue-specific	P	Number of NHPs to evaluate per-voxel concentrations	Percent of tissue-specific ARV area >IC ₅₀
FTC	17	0.7 (0.06-45.1)	0.7 (0.05-39.4)	0.7	3	---
TFV	17	0.6 (0.2-34.5)	0.5 (0.2-21.3)	0.5	14	57.5 (0-100)
EFV	8	15.4 (0.1-96.2)	9.2 (0.1-85.7)	0.8	7	100 (100-100)
RAL	8	0.3 (0.1-1.1)	0.3 (0.1-1.1)	0.5	3	---
MVC	9	80.1 (1.7-91.8)	71.5 (1.6-79.8)	0.2	8	100 (100-100)
ATV	9	0.8 (0.4-53.4)	0.7 (0.3-33.4)	0.4	6	---
Cumulative	17	51.0 (2.9-97.2)	42.2 (2.1-87.6)	0.3		

Data are median (range). Dashes (---) indicate that the low per-voxel sensitivity of FTC and RAL in the spleen tissue precluded per-voxel quantitative analysis to calculate the percent of the tissue-specific area above the respective IC₅₀. P-values calculated via Wilcoxon rank sum test. Abbreviations: ARV, antiretroviral; FTC, emtricitabine; TFV, tenofovir; EFV, efavirenz; RAL, raltegravir; MVC, maraviroc; ATV, atazanavir; NS, not significant; IC₅₀, *in vitro* concentration inhibiting 50% replication.

Table 3. Cell-associated RNA covered by any drug response

ARV	Number of infected NHPs	Number of NHPs with ARV-covered cell-associated virus	Percent of cell-associated virus response covered by ARV
FTC	9	1	0 (0-35.7)
TFV	9	1	0 (0-7.1)
EFV	4	2	46.4 (0-100)
RAL	4	0	0 (0-0)
MVC	5	4	14.2 (0-100)
ATV	5	0	0 (0-0)
Cumulative	9	5	44.4 (0-100)

Data are median (range). Dashes (---) indicate that the low per-voxel sensitivity of FTC in the spleen tissue precluded per-voxel quantitative analyses. N/A indicates that RAL and ATV did not colocalize with cell-associated RNA. Abbreviations: ARV, antiretroviral; FTC, emtricitabine; TFV, tenofovir; EFV, efavirenz; RAL, raltegravir; MVC, maraviroc; ATV, atazanavir.

caRNA & CD20

caRNA & FTC

caRNA & TFV

caRNA & EFV

caRNA & RAL

caRNA & cumulative ARVs

